

The Taming of Dating Precision and Accuracy in ^{14}C -Chronologies. Case Studies at Santorini (Greece) and Tel Rehov (Israel).

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0. Abstract

This report suggests that ongoing debates over Levantine Early Iron Age chronology and the dating of the Santorini eruption largely arise from Bayesian overprecision, as defined by Steier and Rom (200). In both cases, a chronological offset of about 60 years is traced to inappropriate calibration curve shape correction. We further show that distortions in Bayesian summed probability distributions (SPDs) - including spikes, artificial peaks, and systematic shifts - share the same cause. These issues cast serious doubt on the suitability of Bayesian SPDs for dates-as-data demographic analyses, supporting [Heaton et al. \(2025\)](#) whose concerns we share, though noting that such distortions do not occur in CalPal-generated SPDs. The SPD-based barcode seriation (BS) method avoids overprecision distortions and automatically corrects for archaeological sampling bias.

1. Introduction

In a research paper published 25 years ago that offered a very thoughtful critique of the Bayesian sequencing method, Peter Steier and Werner Rom (University of Vienna, ¹⁴C-AMS Laboratory) showed, through computer simulations, that certain assumptions regarding the prior distribution of radiocarbon ages - assumptions embedded within commonly used calibration programs - may inadvertently introduce systematic chronological biases into the resulting posterior distributions (Steier and Rom, 2000). These biases in the modelling output relate to the tendency of Bayesian modelling to produce ¹⁴C-chronologies that have unrealistically high precision, in the present paper termed *overprecision*. This overprecision is accompanied by an artificial shift of results to incorrect ages, that we call *loss of accuracy*. In combination, according to Steier and Rom (2000), the Bayesian algorithm ‘...improves the precision but reduces the accuracy! We demonstrated that these problems show up in any region of the calibration curve. The artifacts are more obvious for a larger sequence of samples but even persist for only two samples’. By use of an exclamation mark, the authors emphasise the significance of this finding. It is an indeed striking – if not outright surprising result.

The present paper examines in detail why the modelling of archaeological radiocarbon data - including, but not limited to, Bayesian approaches - can in certain cases produce substantially misleading results. The issue is explored through an integrated historical and mathematical analysis. The paper proposes a reevaluation of the critical role of the calibration curve in radiocarbon modelling and provides, accordingly, a reinterpretation of the calibration process as a *Fourier transform* (better: Fourier transform *related*) rather than as a problem solvable through the application of Bayesian theory. The applicability of the new approach is explored through case studies of the Santorini (Greece) eruption and the Early Iron Age chronology at Tel Rehov (Israel), both long-standing and still partly contested issues in eastern Mediterranean archaeology.

2. Precision and Accuracy

We begin by briefly reappraising the concepts of precision and accuracy - foundational to nearly all formal measurement frameworks, including the construction of archaeological chronologies - bearing in mind that not all readers have a deep background in statistics.

Figure 1. Single Measurements

Figure 2. Sets of Measurements

As shown in Figure 1, for (N=4) single Gaussian measurements, *precision* reflects the width - more specifically, the spread of each measurement on the underlying time scale, while *accuracy* indicates how close the measurements are to the true age. Another way of viewing these concepts is that *precision* describes how narrowly we can pin down a value from a single measurement, whereas *accuracy* describes how close that measurement is to the target value.

Figure 2 extends these concepts to a larger set of ($M=5$) measurements. Figure 2C shows the ideal case in which all five measurements are tightly clustered (high precision) and centered on the true value (high accuracy). Both Figures 2B and 2D exhibit a broader scatter of measurements (low precision), as commonly encountered in real experiments. However, Figure 2D has a key advantage over Figure 2B: although not shown explicitly, the mean of the five measurements lies on, or very close to, the reference value.

Using a realistic example from Santorini, a calibrated date might first be reported as 3550 ± 70 BCE. After Bayesian calibration with a modelling prior, it could be refined to 3610 ± 10 BCE. Although the standard deviation becomes smaller, suggesting greater precision, the model also shifts the mean date by about 60 years earlier.

3. Terminology

It is essential that, in describing these processes, we employ precise and appropriate terminology (e.g. *successful* vs. *artificial*; *move* vs. *shift*; *shift* vs. *displacement*; *narrowed* vs. *squeezed*; *calibrated* vs. *modelled*; *technical* vs. *conceptual*). The emerging lexicon (rather than mere vocabulary) is both indicative of - and instrumental in - the development of new approaches. This will be most evident when we turn, below, to the newly introduced *mathematical* (vs. *statistical*) concepts of probability. It should also be noted that we avoid the term *probabilistic*. The term originates in the late 1970s and 1980s, when researchers first began to address statistical uncertainty in ^{14}C dates. However, that was long ago and today the term carries an outdated connotation.

From a *technical* perspective, in the example above, the Bayesian posterior has successfully *narrowed* the age range (± 10 BCE, i.e., the standard deviation) relative to the input uncertainty (± 70 BCE), and has also, in parallel, *shifted* the age estimate from 3550 to 3610 BCE. The key question, therefore, is whether this *shift* reflects a genuine *improvement* in inference or an *error* introduced by the model. From a *methodological* standpoint, we may assume that the shift is *intentional* (why else would we be *modelling*?). Conceptually, if the shift is correct, it is a modelling advantage; if incorrect, it is an artificial error. Accordingly, this lexicon contests the view that Bayesian models carry inherent truths, confusing *complexity* with *validity*.

4. A Brief History of Overprecision

The tendency of Bayesian modelling to improve dating precision at the expense of dating accuracy – under certain conditions – is a well-known issue, with studies devoted to finding a solution reaching back at least 25 years (Steier and Rom, 2000; Steier, Rom, Puchegger 2001; Weninger, F., 2010; Weninger, F., 2011). This list emphasises the early contributions of the Vienna group, but many more references can be added, if we extend the subject matter to include neighbouring topics such as modelling sensitivity, robustness and validation. A critical review of Bayesian modelling from archaeological perspective is by Pettitt and Zilhão (2015), and - from the perspective of physics and mathematics - by Weninger et al. (2015), and Weninger and Edinborough (2020). Below, we will reexamine these earlier accounts of radiocarbon calibration framed as a '*Fourier Transform*', drawing primarily on its technical exposition developed by BW as coauthor in Doumet-Serhal et al. (2023).

4a. Precision and Accuracy (Peter Steier and Werner Rom, 2000)

Let us first reconsider the results of Steier and Rom (2000). Their central concern is that Bayesian models can produce artificially precise and potentially misleading chronological estimates, in particular in cases when priors are poorly chosen or insufficiently justified. They note further that mathematical 'artifacts' can arise from certain constraints of the applied methodology, but which are largely hidden to the archaeological user. Their central criticism is that Bayesian Sequencing may produce artificially high dating precision at the cost of dating accuracy (Steier and Rom (2000: 14). They also emphasize that overly strong (restrictive) archaeological priors may cause posterior estimates to be dominated by the shape of the calibration curve rather than the data itself.

Although now roughly 25 years old, this insight remains highly relevant. It helps explain why, across our archaeological case studies, Bayesian-calibrated radiocarbon dates tend to show discrepancies at the steep sections of the calibration curve, next to some particularly long plateaus. The overprecision identified by [Steier and Rom \(2000\)](#) is indeed most pronounced when the archaeological prior aligns with the structure of the calibration curve, although – and entirely in their sense – to understand these phenomena we must move quite some distance beyond the simple assumption that calibration plateaus alone are responsible for the problems.

4b. Robust Bayesian Analysis (Franz Weninger, 2011)

Following [Steier and Rom \(2000\)](#), the most comprehensive research towards Bayesian overprecision to date is that of Franz Weninger (no relation to the author), whose findings were presented in his PhD dissertation entitled *Bayesian Sequencing of Radiocarbon Dates* ([Weninger, F., 2011](#)). The dissertation aimed to analyse and, where possible, reduce intrinsic prior ambiguity in Bayesian sequencing. To achieve this, Franz Weninger developed a MatLab-based variant of robust Bayesian analysis tailored to radiocarbon calibration. The method simultaneously applies all plausible prior distributions consistent with archaeological information and combines the results into a unified outcome. By incorporating multiple models, it safeguards against errors in data, prior assumptions, and modelling choices, ensuring more stable and reliable conclusions. As a result of his extensive studies, Franz Weninger concludes:

‘...robust Bayesian analysis ...generally reduces the precision of the result significantly, or enlarges the resulting highest posterior density ranges ... This is the price one has to pay for producing results with a preferably high reliability that are not affected by the arbitrary choice of a particular prior’.

This raises the question of why the method is not more widely used, given that it offers a reliable default prior for limited archaeological sequencing (e.g. simple “older–younger” relationships). A major strength of OxCal is its dedicated modelling language, which allows transparent formalization of chronological hypotheses and complex relationships such as stratigraphic sequences, phases, and boundaries ([Bronk-Ramsey, 1995; 1998; 2009; 2023](#)); OxCal is further supported by automated generation of OxCal-readable scripts ([Levy et al. 2022](#)).

4c. Philosophical Challenges (Paul Pettitt and João Zilhão, 2015)

Following the early Vienna research (2000–2010), a more accessible, less technical review of Bayesian-critical studies appeared in *World Archaeology* 47, titled ‘Problematizing Bayesian approaches to prehistoric chronologies’ (Pettitt and Zilhão, 2015). As noted by the editors, Paul Pettitt and João Zilhão, Bayesian chronologies rely on assumptions and premises that merit careful consideration. In some cases, these approaches may convey a sense of precision and authority that can mask remaining uncertainties, hidden assumptions, or sources of error. As the authors observe (*ibid.*, p. 526):

‘It is now very easy for archaeologists to deploy Bayesian models themselves, without an understanding of the philosophical and mathematical assumptions on which they are based.’

Which is probably true. Though the point being made is likely that Bayesian methodologies require both rigorous as well as cautious application, if possible reinforced by independent validation of the applied archaeological models, at best in combination with comprehensive sensitivity analyses.

4d. Sensitivity Analysis (János Jakucs et al. 2018)

A particularly instructive archaeological example of growing awareness about the risks of constructing Bayesian chronologies – with risks rooted in the structure of the calibration curve - is provided by Jakucs et al. (2018). Their paper, “*Rows with the Neighbours. The Short Lives of Longhouses at the Neolithic Site of Versend-Gilencsa,*” signals the issue in its very title. The Bayesian results suggest that Linear Bandkeramik (LBK) houses were short-lived, challenging the traditional view that they remained in use for up to a century (cf. Rück, 2009). Yet the Bayesian modelling itself is problematic, and the authors explicitly highlight the intertwined archaeological and statistical dimensions of this interpretive dilemma (Jakucs et al. 2018: 109–110).

‘Obtaining a statistically plausible and stable model for the chronology of Versend has been challenging, due to the shape of the radiocarbon calibration curve between c. 5300 and c. 5000 BC (...). This consists of two small plateaux separated by a pronounced wiggle, which leads to strongly bi-modal posterior distributions. Consequently, the models are extremely slow to converge or are unable to achieve adequate convergence at all (Bronk Ramsey 1995: 429)...

The highest peaks of probability in all of our variant models, however, suggest a short-lived settlement occupied for a few decades around 5200 cal BC. As this coincides with a steep part of the calibration curve separating two small plateaux, we were concerned that our results could be an artefact of the shape of the curve.’

Figure 3. Sensitivity analysis for Early Neolithic data from the site of Versend (Jakucs et al. 2018). This graph provides a multiple-view graph of the Versend chronology. Important is that the calibration curve (IntCal13) shows a steep slope at around 5200 calBC, and two neighbouring plateaus.

A comparison of the chronologies in Figure 3 shows why Bayesian sequencing favours the ultra-short Versend chronology. The method concentrates dates on the steep slope of the calibration curve, maximizing precision. The asymmetrical pull - from younger to older readings - occurs because most dates initially cluster on the younger plateau (5200–5100 calBC). In parallel, the relatively low-lying (and apparently over-smoothed) calibration curve introduces a potentially unrealistic ^{14}C -offset of the archaeological data. This drives OxCal to compress the entire data set onto the slope between the plateaus.

4e. Sensitivity Analysis for the Early Iron Age at Tel Rehov.

The radiocarbon dataset from Tel Rehov plays a central role in discussions of Iron Age chronology in the Southern Levant, including the broader debate between High and Low chronological frameworks. In our view, the solution is trending toward the Low solution (most recently suggested by [Finkelstein and Piasezky, 2023](#)). Regardless, our primary aim in reevaluating the Tel Rehov chronology is to explore the causes and underlying structure of ^{14}C overprecision within a well-defined archaeological context. For this purpose, Tel Rehov offers an exceptional case study, combining a dense corpus of radiocarbon determinations, a well-established stratigraphic sequence, and multiple competing chronological models developed by leading scholars over the past three decades (e.g. [Mazar and Carmi, 2001](#); [Boaretto et al. 2005](#); [Bruins et al. 2003](#)), [Mazar and Bronk-Ramsey, 2008](#); [Fantalkin et al. \(2011\)](#); most recently: [Mazar and Streit, Chapter 48, in: Mazar et al. 2020e](#)). In addition, excavations at Tel Rehov have yielded a large, well-stratified, and exceptionally well-documented pottery assemblage ([Mazar et al. 2020 a-f](#)), which we employ below as an independent framework for pottery-based quality control of the stratigraphic ^{14}C -modelling.

Evidence from Tel Rehov allows partial separation of calibration-curve shape, interlaboratory ^{14}C offsets, and atmospheric ^{14}C fluctuations. As illustrated in [Figure 4](#), Bayesian overprecision is quite similar to Neolithic Versend, reducing the discussion to a small set of key results:

1. The GaussWM model shows a ≥ 20 BP offset between Iron Age IIA dates (N=40) and IntCal20, consistent with Levantine atmospheric ^{14}C effects linked to intra-annual growth differences and regional offsets relative to the trees underlying IntCal20 ([Dee et al. 2010](#); [Manning et al. 2018](#); [2020](#); [2024](#)).
2. Application of GaussWM results in an end-year of 825 ± 13 calBC (Iron Age IIA only). Already this result is practically identical to the excavator's estimate of 840/830 BCE and confirms the excavator's judgement that the invalid Bayesian ages are due to overprecision (cf [Figure 4 caption](#)).

Extending the GaussWM analysis to the Bronze Age strata yields a refined date of 835 ± 8 calBC for the end of Iron Age IIA. The improved precision and slight shift towards an older age are both fully consistent with the increases in sequence length and data size. But the results now align so closely with the excavators' Bronze-Iron Age chronology ([Figure 5](#)) that one becomes curious about the precision of the underlying architectural stratigraphy and pottery-based periodisation.

Figure 4. Sensitivity analysis for the Early Iron Age at Tel Rehov. This graph shows multiple views of the Tel Rehov chronology based on data and information provided by Mazar and Streit (2020). The authors do not accept the results of Bayesian Sequencing, shown here, since they 'contradict the archaeological evidence' by 'squeezing all three strata' of Iron IIA (i.e. Strata VI, V, and IV) into a 'too short time' (ebda 488). As cause of the modelling difficulties the authors infer 'Bayesian squeezing' known from Steier and Rom (2000).

Figure 5. ¹⁴C-Chronology for the Bronze and Early Iron Age at Tel Rehov. Data: Mazar and Streit, 2020. Based on extensive exploratory modelling, the finally selected GaussWM model parameterizes Period IIA as half the duration of Periods IA, IB, and IIB. An offset of -20 BP is applied to all dates, but uncorrected results are practically identical.

Tel Rehov and Beth Shean: Correspondence Analysis (CA)

To assess and quantify the stratigraphic integrity of Tel Rehov, we applied Correspondence Analysis (CA) to pottery data from 54 excavation units and 162 types (12,436 sherds and vessels), supplemented with material from the nearby site of Beth Shean (Mazar et al. 2006). Tel Rehov provides the core Iron Age IIA sequence, extended by Beth Shean into adjacent periods. The datasets are stored separately and jointly in CalPal for future revision.

As brief reminder, CA is a multivariate method widely used in archaeology for pottery seriation. Applied to contingency tables (excavation units as rows, pottery types as columns), it reorders the data to reveal structural relationships, but without altering values. Although CA results are typically displayed as two-dimensional plots, these can be difficult to interpret. For this reason, an additional visualization approach was devised, whereby for easier interpretation the reordered contingency table is visualised as pottery series diagram (Weninger and Krauß, 2020).

Figure 6-8. CA results based on pottery data from Tel Rehov and Beth Shean for the Late Bronze and Early Iron Age. Data: Mazar et al. (2020 a-f); Mazar et al. (2006).

The CA-results are shown in [Figures 6-8](#). The reconstructed patterns of pottery shapes and excavation units align closely with the excavators' periodisation, as illustrated here for data from Areas B and D. The pottery series diagram shows a distinct box-shaped distribution, reflecting internal site dynamics of continuity and destruction. To quantitatively assess the overall precision of the CA dating, we incorporated calibrated ^{14}C results for selected points in the pottery series diagram. This suggests a precision of around ± 10 years for individual Iron IIA excavation units. Further research is needed to assess how the pottery assemblage affects dating precision.

4f. Sensitivity Analysis for the Santorini Eruption Date

The eruption of Thera (Santorini) in Late Minoan IA (LM IA) is a key chronological marker for the Bronze Age Aegean and Eastern Mediterranean. Earlier archaeological chronologies dated it to around 1500 BCE ([Marinatos, 1939](#)). Whereas Bayesian radiocarbon models consistently suggested around 1610 BCE (most recently: [Manning 2024](#)), many archaeological studies favour a younger, probably mid-16th century BCE date (e.g. [Pearson et al. 2018; 2020; 2021; Fantuzzi 2019](#)). An even younger date, around 1525 BCE, is proposed by [Wiener \(2009; 2025\)](#). Reviews of the debate are provided by [Kutschera \(2020\)](#) and [Fantuzzi \(2024\)](#).

Recent studies, particularly [Pearson et al. \(2021, 2023\)](#) and [Erdil et al. 2026](#), now provide updated and altogether highly precise, and consistently measured, annual tree-ring calibration data for the study interval 1700–1500 BCE, but uncertainties persist due to the increasingly complicated plateau shape and possible regional ^{14}C and tree-ring growth differences ([Manning et al. 2018; 2020; 2024](#)).

Figure 9. Sensitivity analysis for the Santorini Eruption Date. The GaussWM results are based on Therasia data (Pearson et al. 2023). The calibration is based on IntCal20 updated with Erdil et al. 2026, but results do not depend on this update.

Figure 9 compares reconstructed Bayesian (OxCal) and non-Bayesian (GaussWM) best-fitting results for the Santorini eruption date. Bayesian results show slope-compression, as forecasted to occur around 1610 BCE (cf. Fig.16). This results in an artificial ~60-year shift, but the exact value remains unclear since the GaussWM analysis highlights the existence of slightly different solutions, depending on the assumed offsets. The possible results are: 1543/1524 BCE: (without offset) and 1529 ± 12 BCE (with offset: -20 ± 5 BP). The younger date is in agreement with Wiener (2009). The Monte Carlo fitting results confirm largely hidden lock-in (quantisation) effects in the Santorini eruption date (Weninger, 1990)

5. Overprecision in Bayesian Summed Probability Distributions

Given the systematic and reproducible distortions in ^{14}C -modelling based on Bayesian Sequencing - demonstrated for the Neolithic at Versend, the Iron Age at Tel Rehov, and the Bronze Age at Santorini - a natural question is whether similar effects also occur in Bayesian-based SPDs? To this topic, since they have very different meanings, we must first differentiate

between Bayesian-calibration (of single ^{14}C -ages) and Bayesian-modelling (of extended data sets).

Figure 10. Single Age Calibration (^{14}C -Age 3790 ± 60 BP). Graphic comparison for Calib810 (Stuiver and Reimer, 1993) and CalPal 2026.1 (Weninger, 1986; 2026)

Figure 10 demonstrates that, for a single radiocarbon age (here: 3790 ± 60 BP), Bayesian and non-Bayesian methods yield indistinguishable results.

Figure 11. Comparison of a Bayesian-SPD with a non-Bayesian SPD. Data from Armit et al. (2014). Redrawn from Heaton (2022: ebda Figure 8).

Figure 11 compares a modelled Bayesian SPD with a non-modelled (call it: Fourier) SPD derived from the same dataset of $N = 2021$ Irish radiocarbon ages (Armit et al. 2014). The initial Bayesian SPD (inset, grey) shows a modest spike at ~ 335 cal AD (1615 cal BP), which is amplified - rather than attenuated - by an advanced Bayesian model (called: “*NP density estimate, Walker*”), producing a smoother curve overall (main panel, violet). Although Heaton (2022) interprets this spike as evidence for post-Irish Dark Age recovery, this interpretation is questionable.

Of greater interest to our topic are substantial age shifts in the Bayesian SPD: a +90-year shift in the main core (ca. 1200–800 calBC) and similarly large –90-year shift on the younger side (200 calBC–200 calAD), in the opposite direction. Comparison with the CalPal-SPD indicates that both shifts are artificial.

In more recent work, Heaton et al. (2025) acknowledge the limitations of earlier Bayesian approaches and advise against further use of SPDs, arguing that their construction is statistically unsound and conceptually incoherent. We strongly endorse this critique, while noting that much of the critique is only valid for Bayesian-based SPDs. To overcome the limitations of the ‘dates-as-data’ approach, we developed barcode-seriation (BS), now routinely used for chronological sequencing across diverse archaeological scales (e.g. dates, sites, phases, periods, cultures) and the broadest possible (local-regional-global) geographic contexts.

4g. Barcode-Seriation (BS): Automated SPD-Sequencing

A key motivation for developing the BS-method (Weninger, 2019; Weninger & Edinborough, 2020) was the combination of substantial archaeological sampling bias with SPD-shape distortion caused by the calibration-curve, which makes the SPD-shape practically impossible to correctly interpret in demographic studies. As a solution, the BS method calculates the SPD but replaces the SPD envelope with a barcode graph that displays the central values of the study dates. The barcode graphs are then arranged chronologically by treating the SPD as an electronic signal and estimating its numerical age using a signal-processing method adapted from nuclear physics. For this purpose, in CalPal-software, a timing discriminator is employed. As illustrated in Figure 12, age sorting can be performed using either leading-edge (SPD-start) or trailing-edge (SPD-stop) amplitude discrimination,

Figure 12. Timing discriminator used in Barcode sequencing. (Upper right) Functional representation of the timing discriminator. (Upper left) Amplitude discrimination applied to an SPD for N=10 calibrated ages. A trailing-edge threshold ($p = 25\%$) yields a sorting age of 8468 calBC. (Lower) This sorting age is assigned to the barcode sequence; the SPD envelope may be omitted to save space on the chronological chart.

Figure 13. Application of barcode-sequencing to a database with (filtered) $N=1686$ dates for $N=34$ Bronze and Iron Age sites from Israel-Palestine, shown in context with climate records from Greenland GISP2 nss K⁺ (Mayewski et al. 1997), Jeita Cave $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ (Cheng et al. 2015), and Tel Dan (Kaniewski et al. 2017).

As demonstrated in [Figure 13](#) for a combined site-culture-subperiod chronology of the Bronze and Iron Age in Israel-Palestine alongside climate records, BS offers clear advantages for constructing archaeological chronologies. It enables an automated overview of the contents of established radiocarbon databases and can partly substitute for Bayesian sequencing and wiggle-matching, while avoiding common risks associated with Bayesian approaches.

6. Mathematical Description of ¹⁴C-Age Calibration based on Fourier Transform

In this section, we attempt to clarify the mathematical origins of Bayesian overprecision. To this purpose we recast the axiomatic framework of radiocarbon calibration used to construct summed probability distributions (SPDs) in terms of the Fourier Transform (not to be confused with a Fourier transformation). Following [Heaton \(2022:2\)](#), SPDs lack a foundation in Bayesian probability theory; however, for CalPal this is unproblematic, as our specific (and very different) SPD construction method has no need for this foundation.

6a Historical Foundation of Fourier-based ¹⁴C-Probability

Instead, we introduce non-Bayesian concepts of probability theory using analogies from Quantum physics. The conceptual framework of Quantum theory-including the Fourier-transform relation between complementary observables and the Born rule for measurement probabilities-originate in John von Neumann's pioneering formalization of quantum mechanics using operator theory and rigorous probability ([von Neumann, 1932; 1955](#)). His work established the mathematical foundations linking Hilbert spaces, observables, and the statistical interpretation of Quantum states.

6b. The Born Rule

We begin with a standard example from quantum physics. Unlike classical physics, where the probability of a wave at a given point in space and time is described by its amplitude Ψ , quantum theory defines this measurable probability by the squared amplitude Ψ^2 , enabling wave-particle behavior. This concept, first introduced by [Born \(1926\)](#), remains the standard description of wave-particles and is also widely used in electrical engineering, where the energy transported by a wave is proportional to Ψ^2 . Less expected, presumably, is that the Born rule can be adapted to the requirements of ¹⁴C age calibration.

This is readily possible for essentially the same reasons as in quantum physics. A long-overlooked point is that ¹⁴C calibration has a number of components that are mathematically equivalent to a Fourier transform. Because both the Born rule and the Heisenberg uncertainty principle also arise from Fourier analysis, an adapted amplitude-squared probability concept naturally explains the observed quantization effects in archaeological ¹⁴C ages, including clustering, age shifts, and amplitude distortions.

6c. The Physical Dimension of the ¹⁴C-Scale

From the Fourier transform perspective, conventional ¹⁴C-ages (expressed in [BP]) have the dimension of inverse time. For example, if time is in seconds [sec], ¹⁴C-ages have dimension [1/sec], reflecting the decay rate. Multiplying a ¹⁴C-age by a calendrical age always yields a dimensionless quantity: [1/sec] × [sec] = [1], and which can then be interpreted as a probability. This holds for any calendrical scale, a property that underpins the Fourier transform's mathematical structure.

The Fourier-based ¹⁴C-calibration starts, as classically, by representing any measured ¹⁴C-age as a Gaussian distribution on the ¹⁴C-scale τ . Eq. (1) then transfers this probability to the calendric scale t using a calibration curve $r(t, \tau)$.

$$\hat{g}(\tau) = \frac{1}{\sigma\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{-\frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{\mu - r(t,\tau)}{\sigma}\right)^2} \quad (\text{Eq.1}) \quad \begin{array}{l} \text{Gaussian Distribution} \\ \text{¹⁴C-Measurement} \end{array}$$

$\tau = \text{Radiocarbon scale [BP]}$
 $\text{¹⁴C-Age: } \mu \pm \sigma_{\mu} \text{ [BP]}$
 $r(t, \tau) \pm \sigma(t, \tau) = \text{Calibration Curve [a, BP]}$
 $\sigma = \sqrt{\sigma_{\mu}^2 + \sigma^2(\tau)} \text{ [BP]}$

Eq. (1) describes a single radiocarbon measurement as a Gaussian distribution with median μ and standard deviation σ . Adding a summation allows linear superposition of multiple ¹⁴C-ages, each requiring individual area normalization. This approach was introduced by Mebus Geyh (~50 years ago) as the ¹⁴C-histogram method ([Geyh, 1983](#)). For simplicity, in Eq.(1) we leave away the summation.

$$\hat{g}(\tau) = \frac{1}{\sigma\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{-\frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{\mu - r(t,\tau)}{\sigma}\right)^2} \quad (\text{Eq.1}) \quad \text{Gaussian } ^{14}\text{C-Domain Measurement}$$

$\tau = \text{Radiocarbon scale [BP]}$
 $^{14}\text{C-Age: } \mu \pm \sigma_\mu [\text{BP}]$
 $r(t,\tau) \pm \sigma(t,\tau) = \text{Calibration Curve [a, BP]}$
 $\sigma = \sqrt{\sigma_\mu^2 + \sigma^2(\tau)} [\text{BP}]$

We now introduce a concept analogous to a unitary operation in quantum theory. In this analogy, just as a unitary operation preserves the number of wave-particles, the probability associated with each Gaussian is normalized so its total area on the ^{14}C -scale equals 1, as expressed in Eq.(2):

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \hat{g}(\tau) d\tau = 1 \quad (\text{Eq.2}) \quad \text{Gaussian } ^{14}\text{C-Domain Normalisation}$$

When this procedure is done before ^{14}C calibration, any later normalization of the study function (for example to account for multiple readings) is unnecessary and forbidden.

6d. The Radiocarbon Fourier Transform

We now define the Fourier Transform as a fundamental principle underlying all subsequent operations. Equations (3) and (4) may seem counterintuitive at first, but essentially, the Fourier Transform acts as a conservation law for probabilities: once a set of ^{14}C -dates is normalized, no further normalization is needed. Archaeologically, Eq.(3) ("Forward Direction") corresponds to calibrating ^{14}C ages to calendar time via the calibration curve, while Eq.(4) ("Inverse Direction") reverses this process, mapping calendar ages back to ^{14}C -ages.

$$g(t) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \hat{g}(\tau) e^{-i\omega\tau} d\tau \quad (\text{Eq.3}) \quad \begin{array}{l} \text{Forward Direction} \\ 14\text{C-Scale} \rightarrow \text{Calendric Scale} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} \text{Fourier Transform} \\ \text{Paired Equations} \\ \tau = \text{Radiocarbon domain [BP]} = [\text{sec}^{-1}] \\ t = \text{Calender domain [sec]} \\ i = \text{imaginary unit} \\ \omega = 2\pi\nu = \text{angular frequency [sec}^{-1}] \end{array}$$

$$\hat{g}(\tau) = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} g(t) e^{i\omega t} dt \quad (\text{Eq.4}) \quad \begin{array}{l} \text{Inverse Direction} \\ \text{Calendric Scale} \rightarrow 14\text{C-Scale} \end{array}$$

Although $\hat{g}(\tau)$ and $g(t)$ appear as two functions, they are actually the same function viewed from different perspectives: $\hat{g}(\tau)$ on the ^{14}C -scale and $g(t)$ on the calendric time scale. Both represent the same ^{14}C -dating probability."

Using the Born Rule, Eq. (5) gives the probability $p(x,t)$ as $\Psi(x,t)$ times $\Psi^*(x,t)$. Complex-number interpretation is irrelevant in our application, and since ^{14}C - and calendar-age products are dimensionless, this quantum probability directly defines a probability concept that can be used in archaeological ^{14}C -chronology (Eq. 6).

$$p(x,t) = \iint \Psi(x,t) \Psi^*(x,t) dx dt = 1 \quad (\text{Eq.5}) \quad \begin{array}{l} \text{Probability Definition in Quantum Theory (Born Rule)} \\ P = \text{Normalised probability defined for product of} \\ \text{wave-function } \Psi(x,t) \text{ and its complex conjugate} \\ \Psi^*(x,t) \text{ under Fourier Transform.} \end{array}$$

$$p(t,\tau) = \iint g(t) \hat{g}(\tau) dt d\tau = 1 \quad (\text{Eq.6}) \quad \begin{array}{l} \text{Application of Born Rule in Radiocarbon Analysis.} \\ P = \text{Normalised probability defined for the product of the} \\ \text{Gaussian function } \hat{g}(\tau) \text{ in the } ^{14}\text{C}\text{-domain and its twin} \\ \text{associated cal-domain function } g(t) \text{ under Fourier Transform.} \end{array}$$

$$p(x,t) = N \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} |\Psi(x,t)|^2 dt = 1$$

(Eq.7) Born Rule: Probability definition.

P = Normalised probability defined for squared amplitude of wave-function $\Psi(x,t)$, with optional scale factor N to cover a finite number of ^{14}C -dates.

Note, that only one wave function Ψ is used to describe any number N of individual ^{14}C -ages, even though each of these may belong to a different sample.

7. The Cause of SPD-spikes

Next, we explore the effect of applying a second normalization to the data, to see what happens if a mathematically forbidden operation is purposely applied (see Eq. 2). The result is illustrated in Figure 14.

Figure 14. Cause of SPD spikes inferred from a comparison of different SPD construction methods (redesigned from Weninger et al. 2011). This figure shows four SPD graphs from the same ^{14}C dataset (Bueno et al. 2013). By default, CalPal applies only primary area-normalisation. To eliminate calibration curve artifacts, OxCal (as we infer) applies secondary normalisation; however, Bayesian SPD construction - regardless of the underlying cause - produces spikes, which led Bueno et al. (2013) to SPD-smoothing.

Crucially, the applied secondary “normalisation” is counterproductive: rather than correcting calibration curve variability, it introduces pronounced spikes at steep slopes. These slopes are flanked by plateaus - a pattern characteristic of overprecision in Bayesian sequencing.

10. Forecasting of Modelling Overprecision

An essential requirement for avoiding overprecision in Bayesian sequencing and SPD construction is to forecast where and why chronological distortions arise within the calibration system. Since both methods likely share the same source of distortion - secondary area-normalization being essentially equivalent to calendar-curve corrections - this can be addressed by explicitly applying secondary area-normalization. The issue is easiest to examine in SPD construction.

For SPD-based forecasting purposes, the Fourier transform indicates that the discrete, particle-like characteristics of ^{14}C ages are more significant than their continuous, wave-like components. In accordance with the Born rule, by applying a squared-amplitude transformation to the SPD-construction we can further enhance the exact age-localisation of the requested calibration curve structures. This is also supported by using Gaussians with small errors (± 10 BP), omitting calibration curve errors altogether, and not applying aesthetic (annual-scale) SPD-smoothing. When this approach is used to back-calibrate a uniform sample, it significantly increases the peak–trough contrast in the SPD, sharpens the resulting dating probabilities, and more clearly isolates intervals in which calibration nonlinearities could bias Bayesian chronological modelling.

Figure 15. Forecasting of Ages for occurrence of Bayesian Overprecision. Method: A uniform input sample sequence (1 sample every 2 yrs; with assigned ^{14}C -scale error $\sigma=\pm 10$ BP) is folded by INTCAL20 to produce a characteristic sequence of peaks and troughs. The SPD-peaks represent the plateaus of the calibration curve. The troughs represent the steep regions. To accenuate events in steep regions, the back-calibrated ^{14}C -histogram is squared.

As shown in [Figure 15](#) for the time interval 1800–800 calBC, age distortions can be expected for ages around 1615, 1210, 1000, 905, and 800 BCE. The predicted distortions for 1615 calBC and 905 calBC are already well known: within minimal error limits (a few yrs) the former age is linked to the (supposed) Santorini eruption (cf. [Figure 9](#): ~1610 calBC); the latter to the (supposed) end of the Early Iron Age at Tel Rehov (cf. [Figure 4](#): ~890 calBC). In both cases, Bayesian overprecision results from the calibration curve's structure, where a steep section lies between two plateaus. In practical applications, this effect can be substantially amplified by what appear to be only minor data offsets. As shown above for possible growth-period differences in the eastern Mediterranean on the order of 20 BP, even a shift of this small magnitude can transfer a considerable portion of probability mass from a calibration plateau to a steep slope. As a result, the Bayesian posterior may contract dramatically, effectively collapsing into a single, narrow interval.

Discussion

CalPal sequencing with GaussWM is only partly less sensitive to such calibration-curve structures. Like OxCal, it can show overprecision and false offsets. When for the first time directly confronted with these effects in the Varna Necropolis data ([Krauß et al. 2017](#)), we replaced the conventional chi-squared statistic with a non-central chi-squared IMSL procedure. Subsequent experience shows that, with $\lambda = 10$, systematic ^{14}C offsets up to ~20 BP can often - though not always - be accommodated without obvious distortion. We emphasise, however, that overprecision does not necessarily explain (for example) the differing Varna cemetery durations estimated by CalPal-GaussWM (250 yrs) and OxCal-Bayes (120–160 yrs). To answer this question, we must consider not only the chronology itself, but also the underlying statistical philosophy. In the case of GaussWM, the numerical outputs are designed as envelope values. As precise as possible – but not too precise – is a natural challenge for all statistical procedures.

Conclusions and Outlook

This report contends that the protracted debates surrounding both the chronology of the Levantine Early Iron Age as well as the date of Santorini eruption are, to a considerable extent, the result of Bayesian overprecision. Extending the arguments advanced by [Steier and Rom \(2000\)](#), the present analysis suggests that Bayesian overprecision produces an age offset that can be quantified. In both instances, a systematic offset of approximately 60 years is apparent. This value is about half the length of the relevant plateaus, after which the overprecision reverses its direction (cf. [Figure 11](#)). This requires further studies. Otherwise, the age distortions identified for Bayesian-SPDs are similar in size and pattern to those seen in Bayesian sequencing, with two plateaus separated by a steep slope: we have succeeded in *accurately* forecasting the ages for overprecision, although not their magnitudes.

[Crema and Bevan \(2021\)](#) confirm our proposal ([Weninger et al. 2011](#)) that spikes and other artefacts in SPDs result from repeated area normalisation. By analogy, we suggest that the overprecision seen in Bayesian sequencing may also stem from such normalisation. Since area normalisation attempts to correct the calibration curve shape - something that is mathematically impossible – this may undermine the objectives of Bayesian modelling.

Our proposed “Fourier-transform” (or “quantum-theoretical”) framework is also mathematically incomplete. Radiocarbon calibration involves a one-sided uncertainty relation, whereas quantum theory assumes a symmetric two-sided correspondence between time and frequency ([Weninger et al. 2011](#), p. 15). Thus, the analogy to quantum theory should be taken *cum grano salis*. A more rigorous mathematical treatment lies beyond the scope of the present paper.

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